

A Study on Quality of work-life among my friends during Covid-19 pandemic in Bangalore

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ABSTRACT

During Pandemic, particularly the covid-19 surge in India, it continues us to push our limits to the unknown depths – as a working professional and as an individual's we seek to do our best and serve the organization and also ensure our families, friends and communities are also taken care.

It is proved that many organizations have prioritized their employee wellbeing by giving required support during the Covid-19 pandemic. At the same time, working from home has erased the limits on the time that is dedicated to working and the time dedicated to oneself.

During this challenging environment, Quality of work-life plays an important role for both working professionals and also for Organizations. This research paper aims to study the Quality of work-life among my friends in Bangalore during the pandemic situation. The sample data consists of people working in different workstreams in Bangalore city. The data is collected through an online mode by sending the Google form having standard survey questionnaire by Marshall Sashman & Langermann. This instrument consists of two parts 1. Quality of work-life condition having 25 questions/items 2. Quality of work-life feeling having 10 questions/Items. This research study has been conducted using the instrument called Quality of work-life feeling, as most of the employees are working remotely during this Covid-19 pandemic.

Quality of work-life (QWF) – Feeling, is descriptive in nature, the researcher has used a non-parametric test which is Mann Whitney U Test as an inferential study.

The statistical work for this study is carried out using MS Excel and Python environment

Keywords – Quality of Work-life (QWF), Job Satisfaction, Feelings

1.INTRODUCTION

In today's pandemic, we understand the importance of relationships and trying to equilibrium between work and our personal life.

Covid-19 pandemic has created an environment that has made to view the work and home lives under the same roof for many working professions and it is a current challenge for most of us to manage both successfully.

Most of the companies have come forward to support employees by providing childcare, physical wellness, and mental health facilities. Few Organizations like Genpact, Accenture, SAP, Tata Group, Wipro, and many more have provided benefits to employees during a pandemic

1. Monetary benefits to support the work environment
2. Online Wellness support
3. Online Yoga and meditation training
4. Online support for medicines related to Covid
5. Free Doctor consultation
6. Free RTPCR Test and Free Vaccination drives

QWL also plays a vital role in controlling attrition in an organization. It correlates to the level of satisfaction and the level of dissatisfaction among the individuals. It is a controlled approach for most organizations. The best organizations are those that regularly invest in employees towards their growth and development through new learning.

Importance of Quality of work-life

QWL leads to an atmosphere of better interpersonal development with high motivation level. During the pandemic, regular production-related meeting, Performance meetings, Training, Brainstorming sessions, regular feedback on work, health check, and constant support would increase the productivity and QWL which would lead to the overall development of an employee

Below are a few of Work-life condition and feelings

- Job Satisfaction
- Work-life balance
- Comfortable work environment
- Financial reimbursement (Reward, Pay, Incentives)
- Managerial factors
- Career promotion
- Clear Job expectation

Job Satisfaction

Satisfaction level of a person gets from the work they are doing can be related to their attitude. Job Satisfaction is a very individualistic aspect of work as satisfaction, in many ways, reflects how the person views not only how they do their job but also how the organization views how they do the job and who they are as a person. Many factors are associated with job satisfaction like recognition, monetary benefits, growth and responsibility along with compensation.

Firstly, people are deserved to be treated fairly and with respect. Job satisfaction is a mirror image of humanistic approach. It is an indicator of emotional and psychological health. Secondly, the functional view point is that the behavior of an employee with respect to job satisfaction affects organization.

In general, Job satisfaction is influenced by the following factors

Level of job

Job contents

Leadership

Pay

Promotional opportunities

Social interaction

2. OBJECTIVE

1. To explore the QWL– Feeling among the individuals
2. Is there a relationship between Work environment and the Quality work life
3. Is there a relationship between Work Condition and the Quality work life

3. METHODOLOGY

This research paper studies only the QWL - Feeling among the working professionals as most of the employees are working remotely during the pandemic.

The research methodology used to study the QWL is a survey method through the standard questionnaire by Marshall Sashkin and langermann. This instrument consist of 10 questions/Items related to Feelings

Data is collected online by creating the questionnaire in a Google form and sharing the link to the respondents. Instructions are given in the Google form and all doubts are clarified before submitting the form. Google form has been creating in such a way that the form would be submitted only after answering all the questions

Instructions are given for individual before filling the Quality of work-life– Feelings form

Read each statement carefully and indicate your response below with the succeeding keys

1. SD – Strongly Dis-agree
2. D – Dis-Agree
3. U – Uncertain
4. A – Agree
5. SA – Strongly Agree

4.RESPONDENTS

The researcher used a convenient sampling method and there are 52 respondents. This study was conducted from April 2021 till May 2021 during the peak time of Covid-19 in Bangalore.

The data collected through respondents have different lengths of service and different working streams which contain individuals working in corporate and non-corporate environments.

Figure 1: The above Graph represents the number of Respondents with Current years of experience

Figure 2: The above Graph represents the number of Respondents with Total years of experience

Working Environment

Figure 3: The above Pie chart shows the number of respondents working in IT and Non-IT

5.TOOLS FOR THE DATA COLLECTION

The information related to the study was collected through an online survey method

Below is the list of tools required:

1. Quality of work-life Questionnaire by Marshall Sashkin and Langermann with an instrument of Feelings having 10 questions
2. Google form created having the list of questionnaires and also the instructions
3. MS Excel and Python for Exploratory Analysis and Statistical analysis

6.RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The Quality of work-life test was administered on 52 respondents working in both Corporate and non-corporate environment

The analysis is carried out using the Excel functions, correlation, and Man Whitney U-test.

The following table explains the analysis of various dimensions of the variables used for Quality of work life.

Figure 4: Represents the percentage of people preference of work post-covid situation

Here 50% of the respondents selected to work in a Hybrid environment which has the flexibility of working both at home and the office and 38% of the respondent would opt to work from home and only 12% of the respondent opted to work from Office

Figure 5: Respondents were asked if they like the sort of work that they are doing and 52% of Agree and 40% of strongly agree that they like the sort of work they are doing

Below are the percentage responses for each of the questions

Figure 6: Respondents were asked if their job gives an opportunity to carry out the things that he/she do best and 61% Agree and 27% strongly agree that they like the sort of work they are doing

Figure 7: Respondents were asked on the pride and accomplishment and 59% Agree and 27% strongly agree.

Figure 8: Respondents were asked if their job is an important job and 56% Agree and 34% strongly agree that their job is important.

Figure 9: Respondents were asked if their job is a rewarding experience and 63% Agree and 27% strongly agree that their job is a rewarding experience

Figure 10: Respondents were asked regarding if they were inherited money without working and 45% Agree and 21% strongly agree

Figure 11: Respondents were asked, on retirement and 35% Dis-agree and 23% Agree

Figure 12: Respondents were asked on paycheck and 33% Dis-Agree and 23% Agree.

Figure 13: Respondents were asked on the interests outside of the job and 39% Agree and 27% Dis-agree

Figure 14: Respondents were asked on importance of work and 51% Agree and 31% strongly agree.

Below tables presents the Mean and Standard deviation of each of the variables by the researcher on the Quality of Work-life

1.

count	52.000000
mean	4.307692
std	0.672673
min	2.000000
25%	4.000000
50%	4.000000
75%	5.000000
max	5.000000

2.

count	52.000000
mean	4.134615
std	0.657650
min	2.000000
25%	4.000000

50%	4.000000
75%	5.000000
max	5.000000

3.

count	52.000000
mean	4.096154
std	0.721100
min	2.000000
25%	4.000000
50%	4.000000
75%	5.000000
max	5.000000

4.

count	52.000000
mean	4.250000
std	0.622298
min	3.000000
25%	4.000000
50%	4.000000
75%	5.000000
max	5.000000

5.

count	52.000000
mean	4.134615
std	0.686818

min	2.000000
25%	4.000000
50%	4.000000
75%	5.000000
max	5.000000

6.

count	52.000000
mean	3.557692
std	1.227359
min	1.000000
25%	3.000000
50%	4.000000
75%	4.000000
max	5.000000

7.

count	52.000000
mean	3.423077
std	1.193876
min	1.000000
25%	2.000000
50%	4.000000
75%	4.000000
max	5.000000

8.

count	52.000000
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mean	3.365385
std	1.172041
min	1.000000
25%	2.000000
50%	4.000000
75%	4.000000
max	5.000000

9.

count	52.000000
mean	3.057692
std	1.211278
min	1.000000
25%	2.000000
50%	3.000000
75%	4.000000
max	5.000000

10.

count	52.000000
mean	4.000000
std	0.949716
min	1.000000
25%	4.000000
50%	4.000000
75%	5.000000
max	5.000000

Correlation Study

Below is the Correlation Study using the Spearman Rank method using Python, the variables used are preferred work environment and the QWF and the study found that there is a positive correlation between the people who preferred to work from the Office and the people who preferred to work in Both Home and Office and negative correlation on the people preferred to work from the office and home and also from both and Home.

Figure 15: Correlation representation using Python.

Further to the Correlation study, the researcher conducted the Mann-Whitney U test to find the significant difference and the test was conducted under a Python environment using the Mann-whitney U module

Mann-whitney P-value for the QWF

1. The P-Value among the group where people opted to work both in the Office and At Home and those who opted to work only at Home during the pandemic situation is 0.08

```
MannwhitneyuResult(statistic=1143.5, pvalue=0.08810319828632879)
```

2. The P-Value among the group where people opted to work both in the Office and At Home and those who opted to work only at the Office during the pandemic situation is 0.2

```
MannwhitneyuResult(statistic=1224.5, pvalue=0.20448113890861164)
```

3. The P-Value among the group where people opted to work only at the Office and those who opted to work only at Home during the pandemic situation is 0.08

MannwhitneyuResult(statistic=1136.5, pvalue=0.08108434926912367)

4. The P-Value among the group where people who are IT and Non-IT during the pandemic situation is 0.0004

MannwhitneyuResult(statistic=844.0, pvalue=0.0004831601530506625)

Overall Study gives a Score of 38.32 by taking an Average Individual Total Score in Quality of work-life Feelings which is Interpreted as a “Good” Score. This implies that the overall sample population is happy with the job, feels that his job is important, and is having a rewarding experience. They also have a sense of pride in their job and a sense of accomplishment in performing the job.

7. CONCLUSION

Quality of work-life plays an important role for employees to ensure they are happy with less stressed, motivated, and are healthy with fewer instances of sickness and absenteeism, for an organization it is important to retain their employees, increase the loyalty of employees, and to increased productivity and quality of work. Better QWF mains to an environment of good interpersonal development and high motivation. Finally, a high level of QWF leads to Job Satisfaction resulting in outstanding performance.

Mann-Whitney U test result concludes that

a. The QWF– Feelings among those working from Office or Home or Both (Office and Home) fails to assume that there is a difference in means.

b. That the QWF– Feelings between the IT and Non-IT signifies that there is at least one significant difference stating that the difference in means is significant.

Finally, the study concludes that the QWF among my friends has “GOOD” feelings about their work.

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